

Electrification of Rural Health Centers in Rwanda Using Energy Access Explorer

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Executive Summary

The report prioritizes the electrification of rural health centres in Rwanda using the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) platform to guide electrification planning. With datasets selected in EAE, Population, distribution lines, global horizontal irradiation, Relative wealth Index and accessibility to cities; the results show two scenarios, areas far away from existing distribution line, >2km, these areas can be electrified using off-Grid solutions, i.e solar. Hence the health centers located in these areas can benefit from this source of energy by getting electricity. The second scenario are the areas that are near the distribution lines, at the distance less than 2 km from the grid, these areas can get electricity from the grid by its expansion and are said to be Grid connected. The health centers that are in these areas can get electricity for the grid. The report shows that in Rwanda on Grid and Off grid connection is possible and this is not different from the reality as the utility report shows the use of these two sources of electricity. The Government of Rwanda should continue to use both off grid and on grid solutions as source of electricity; this can be cost effective in electrification projects.

Key Findings

In the off-grid scenario, the majority of the areas are in the high and medium energy access potential. Results from top priority locations indicates that health centres that are mostly within 2km or higher, the relative wealth index is low hence most people are poor.

Key results demonstrate that while the rural areas have significant potential for off-grid solar installations, some facilities can benefit from grid connectivity due to proximity to existing infrastructure further to this, solar backup can be used for grid reliability.

For top potential grid connections, most areas are characterized with short distance to the facility, high relative wealth index therefore they have high ability to pay and high population.

Recommendations

Prioritize off-grid solar systems in rural health centres located in areas with high solar energy potential since these are feasible and cost-effective in remote locations where grid extension is not feasible. Apart from solar systems, the Ministry of infrastructure should develop solar and hydro mini-grids in rural areas that have a significant demand.

The Energy Development Corporation Limited (EDCL) must prioritize grid extension in the clusters identified as close to existing infrastructure. This will provide reliable electricity to areas where it is most practical to expand the grid.

1. Introduction

Access to electricity is a one Indicator for Economic Transformation of National Strategic Transformation Phase II (NST2) in Rwanda, NST2 is designed to build on these achievements and take the country closer to realizing the Vision 2050 of sustainable economic growth, prosperity and high quality of life for all citizens. Specifically, the one goal of Rwanda Vison 2050 is to have 100% electricity access by 2030 (Republic of Rwanda, 2024) as of June 2024, households' access to electricity was 78.9%, with 55.9% On grid and 23% Off grid connected mostly solar.

With datasets selected in EAE, Population, distribution lines, global horizontal irradiation, Relative wealth Index and accessibility to cities; the results show two scenarios, areas far away from existing distribution line, >2km, these area can be electrified using Off-Grid solutions, here the potential source of energy is solar. Hence the health centers loacated in these areas can benefit from this source of energy by getting electricity. The second scenario are the areas that are near the distribution lines, at the distance less than two km from the grid, these areas can get electricity from the grid by its expansion and are said to be Grid connected. The health centers that are in these areas can get electricity for the grid. The report shows that in Rwanda on Grid and Off grid connection is possible and this is not different from the reality as the utility report shows the use these two source of electricity.

Rwanda is one of countries globally with high rate of electricity connection, from 6% in 2009 to 78.9%, as of June 2024 of households access to electricity, with 55.9% on-grid connected and 23% off grid connected mostly solar. The lack of reliable energy, particularly in rural areas where 72.1% of the population resides (National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda, 2023), poses challenges to healthcare facilities. This report explores the use of the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) to identify optimal areas for electrification of rural health centers through both off-grid and

grid-extension methods. The goal is to enhance access to electricity for essential services and improve the quality of life in rural areas of Rwanda.

2. Methodology

Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The Energy Access Explorer (EAE) platform was employed to assess areas of Rwanda that would benefit most from electrification, focusing on healthcare facilities in rural areas. The EAE is an innovative tool designed to visualize and analyze data related to energy access, enabling the identification of high potential areas for renewable implementation. Most data for the analysis were from Rwanda Energy Group and other sources.

Table 1: Off grid Demand Index Dataset

Dataset	Unit	Range	Selected Range	Importance
Health Facilities	proximity in km	min: 0, max: 250	min: 0, max: 250	3
Relative Wealth Index	proximity in km	min: -2, max: 2	min: -2, max: 2	3
Population density	ppl/km ²	min: 0, max: 100000	min: 0, max: 100000	3

Table 2: Off grid Supply Index Dataset

Dataset	Unit	Range	Selected Range	Importance
Global Horizontal Irradiation	proximity in km	min: 500, max: 2800	min: 1000, max: 2800	3
Distribution lines	proximity in km	min: 0, max: 700	min: 2, max: 700	3

Table 3: On grid Demand Index Dataset

Dataset	Unit	Range	Selected Range	Importance
Health Facilities	proximity in km	min: 0, max: 250	min: 0, max: 5	3
Relative Wealth Index	proximity in km	min: -2, max: 2	min: -2, max: 2	3
Population density	ppl/km ²	min: 0, max: 100000	min: 0, max: 100000	3

Table 4: On grid Supply Index Dataset

Dataset	Unit	Range	Selected Range	Importance
Accessibility to cities	proximity in km	min: 0, max: 2000	min: 0, max: 2000	3
Distribution lines	proximity in km	min: 0, max: 700	min: 0, max: 2	3

The EAE integrates multiple datasets, the model included solar irradiation, proximity distribution lines, population density, and accessibility to cities. This approach allowed the identification of priority areas for energy interventions. Two scenarios were analysed. Firstly, the Off-Grid Scenario which assessed the feasibility of using off-grid source as source of electricity, i.e. solar systems to electrify remote rural areas. The scenario considered factors such as health facilities, relative wealth index, population, solar potential (Global Horizontal Irradiation > 1600kWh/m²) and proximity to distribution lines or from grid (>2km).

Secondly the Grid Scenario that evaluated areas closer to existing grid infrastructure, using criteria like health facilities, relative wealth index, population, accessibility to cities and proximity to distribution lines(<2km).

3. Results

After data upload in the EAE Platform and run, the below results were produced;

Table 1: Share of area for each Index in km², On-Grid

Index	low	low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential	76	2,048	7,790	7,561	1,193
Demand Index	122	3,301	10,428	4,456	361
Supply Index	162	2,061	3,169	6,760	6,516
Assistance Need Index	274	4,141	9,405	4,442	406

Table 2: Share of population for each Index, on Grid

Index	Low	Low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential	15,861	745,606	3,603,380	4,910,092	2,345,351
Demand Index	18,660	1,229,496	5,196,776	3,736,943	1,438,415
Supply Index	54,284	841,267	1,429,384	4,001,445	5,293,910
Assistance Need Index	121,048	2,543,845	6,139,182	2,590,388	225,827

Table 3: Share of area for each Index in km², off Grid

Index	low	low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential	33	416	3,382	1,147	20
Demand Index	82	702	3,350	850	14
Supply Index	33	55	478	2,103	2,329
Assistance Need Index	37	440	3,178	1,269	74

Table 4: Share of population for each Index, off Grid

Index	low	low-med	medium	med-high	high
Energy Access Potential	273	39,915	1,129,014	621,005	18,961
Demand Index	1,229	107,149	1,168,154	516,439	16,197
Supply Index	11,852	26,840	176,359	741,399	852,718
Assistance Need Index	872	51,558	1,054,147	646,393	56,198

According to the above tables, a large number of people in Rwanda are connected on national Grid as shown in the table 1&2, it means that people in those areas access health centers with electricity from the grid. Table 3&4 shows people living in rural areas that access health centers need electricity supply from off Grid sources, i.e solar.

Figure 1. Location with Highest EAI Index, Off-Grid

Table 5: 20 top Locations with highest EAI Index (Off-Grid)

	provinces	POI	Long/Lat	EAI	ANI	Demand	Supply
1	Southern Province		[29.7600, -2.6453]	high	med-high	high	high
2	Kigali City		[30.1104, -2.0529]	high	medium	high	high
3	Northern Province		[30.0924, -1.5860]	high	high	high	med-high
4	Eastern Province		[30.3080, -2.1876]	high	medium	med-high	high
5	Western Province		[28.8887, -2.4209]	high	high	high	high
6	Eastern Province		[30.4338, -1.2178]	high	medium	high	high
7	Eastern Province		[30.4338, -1.2358]	high	medium	high	high
8	Eastern Province		[30.4338, -1.2268]	high	medium	high	high
9	Southern Province		[29.7241, -2.3312]	high	medium	med-high	high
10	Eastern Province		[30.4428, -1.2178]	high	medium	high	high
11	Southern Province		[29.7151, -2.3312]	high	medium	med-high	high
12	Eastern Province		[30.3619, -1.6040]	high	medium	high	high
13	Eastern Province		[30.4428, -1.2358]	high	medium	high	high
14	Northern Province		[29.6522, -1.4693]	high	high	high	medium
15	Western Province		[29.0234, -2.6991]	high	medium	med-high	high
16	Northern Province		[29.6433, -1.4693]	high	high	high	medium
17	Kigali City		[30.1373, -2.0260]	high	medium	med-high	high
18	Eastern Province		[30.8201, -2.2145]	high	medium	med-high	med-high
19	Western Province		[28.8797, -2.5466]	high	medium	med-high	med-high
20	Eastern Province		[30.4877, -1.7925]	high	medium	med-high	high

Figure 2. Location with the Highest EAI Index, Off-Grid

From Off-grid scenario, the results show that the available renewable energy resources, solar potential for all the selected areas was at least 1600kWh/m² and the highest 1915kWh/m² in the top 20 areas, fig.3. The rural health centres have a potential for SHS and grid solar energy solution based on the location of the facility. Meanwhile off-grid solutions are viable in sparsely populated regions where grid extension would be cost-prohibitive.

On grid scenario, the results indicate that most health centres are within a radius of 1km, location with Highest EAI Index shown on fig. 4. The average population of first 20 locations with Highest EAI Index is 6429 ppl/km². the closeness to existing distribution lines makes the areas identified suitable for grid connections. These facilities are located in areas with relatively better infrastructure, and the relative wealth index is high for all areas >1 making grid extensions more feasible.

4. Discussion

The results highlight the need for a dual approach to rural electrification in Rwanda that are off grid and grid connections. Off-grid solutions are suitable in areas where the facility is far from the Grid and these are suitable and provide a sustainable method for electrifying remote health centers. It is cost effective and relatively cheaper compared to extending the grid to areas far from the national grid. Grid extensions should be prioritized in areas where facilities are closer to existing infrastructure. Reliable electricity would enable improved healthcare delivery, particularly for life-saving equipment and cold storage for vaccines, as well as providing light during night-time.

Policy recommendations

The Rwanda Ministry of Infrastructure (MININFRA) should prioritize the development and deployment of off-grid renewable energy solutions, particularly solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, in rural areas where grid extension is not feasible. This approach can significantly improve access to electricity in remote health centres.

Future Work Research

The EAE is a significant tool in mapping out areas that require energy access, therefore, it is important to consider how the tool can be used in the development of a more integrated and inclusive energy planning. This includes the importance of coordinating a working group for an EAE sustainability plan and continuous data collection among members

Limitations of study

The main limitation is accurate and reliable data, recent data and missing data for some datasets in Rwanda.

5. Conclusion

The Energy Access Explorer is an effective tool in identifying priority areas for electrification in rural areas of Rwanda. For Off-grid scenario, solar solution should be prioritized for remote health centres, while the grid extensions can support facilities located near existing infrastructure.

Many rural health centres in Rwanda are located in areas with high solar energy potential, Off-grid solar solutions are often more feasible and cost-effective than grid extension in these regions, particularly in remote and sparsely populated areas. All in all, Using the EAE has provided precise data that will enable efficient planning, ensuring that resources are allocated to areas where they will have the greatest impact.

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